

FREQUENCY OF INDIRECT HYPERBILIRUBINEMIA IN PREMATURE NEONATES IN THE NEONATOLOGY UNIT OF HAYATABAD MEDICAL COMPLEX, PESHAWAR

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Abstract

Background: Indirect hyperbilirubinemia is still one of the most prevalent problems among preterm newborns, especially in low- and middle-income countries. Immaturity in bilirubin metabolism, higher bilirubin burden, and delayed identification all raise the likelihood of severe illness and bilirubin-induced neurological dysfunction. The aim of this study was to assess the prevalence and risk factors for indirect hyperbilirubinemia in preterm newborns hospitalized to the neonatology unit of Hayatabad Medical Complex in Peshawar.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was undertaken from November 1st, 2024 to April 30th, 2025. A total of 196 preterm newborns (gestational ages 28-36 weeks) were recruited via non-probability sequential sampling. The sample size was derived using the WHO single proportion formula, with a 15% predicted prevalence. Indirect hyperbilirubinemia was defined as total bilirubin >1.5 mg/dL and indirect fraction >1.2 mg/dL. Relevant demographic and clinical data were gathered. Data were evaluated using SPSS v25, and $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results: The average gestational age was 33.26 ± 2.34 weeks and the average birth weight was 1.88 ± 0.43 kg. Indirect hyperbilirubinemia was seen in 26% of neonates, with 68.6% mild, 27.5% moderate, and 3.9% severe. Gestational age was significantly associated with hyperbilirubinemia ($p = 0.012$), with the highest occurrence occurring between 28 and 31 weeks. There were no significant relationships with gender, mode of delivery, birth weight, or socioeconomic status.

Conclusion: Indirect hyperbilirubinemia affects one in every four preterm neonates, especially those with lower gestational age. Early screening, consistent phototherapy regimens, and increased community awareness are critical for decreasing severe disease and complications.

INTRODUCTION

Low birth weight and prematurity is a major factor contributing in neonatal mortality 28% cases. Incidence of prematurity among newborns is about 23%. In China, preterm birth rate is 13.6 million most of them die during curly neonatal period due to fatal complication 72 % of neonatal mortality is due to prematurity.¹ World health organization define prematurity as any delivery before 37 weeks of gestations, New born between 32 – 37 weeks are late preterm and 28 to 32 weeks are very preterm and before 28 weeks as extreme preterm babies.² Risk of complications increase with decreasing gestational age very and extreme preterm are more prone to complications like respiratory distress syndrome and necrotizing enterocolitis. Hyperbilirubinemia and metabolic abnormalities are putting lot of burden on nurseries and cost to parents, society and health sectors.³ Direct complications of preterm birth were responsible for an estimated 35% of the world's 3 million neonatal deaths in 2010, making preterm birth the second most common cause of death in children under-five after pneumonia. Preterm birth also increases the risk of death due to other causes, especially neonatal infections. Hyperbilirubinemia and hypothermia are other complications of preterm birth.⁴ Preterm birth is associated with many specific acute complications of immaturity including respiratory distress syndrome, intracranial hemorrhage, necrotising enterocolitis, and retinopathy of prematurity (ROP). In almost all high- and middle-income countries, preterm birth is the leading cause of child deaths. 23% mortality in preterm neonates is due to hypothermia, hypoglycemia, hypocalcaemia and hyperbilirubinemia.⁵ Frequency of hypocalcaemia and hypoglycemia, and indirect hyperbilirubinemia was 46%, 32% and 15% in a study.⁶ This study was therefore designed to address the gap in local epidemiology data on indirect

hyperbilirubinemia in preterm neonates in Pakistan. Although hyperbilirubinemia is a well-known consequence of preterm, its true prevalence and distribution across gestational age groups in our setting are underreported. Early detection and prompt treatments are critical in preventing bilirubin-induced brain damage and related morbidity. Obtaining local data from the neonatology unit at Hayatabad Medical Complex in Peshawar will assist doctors in improving risk assessment, guiding treatment procedures, and supporting more effective family counselling. This, in turn, can help to improve newborn outcomes and optimize resource use in tertiary care settings.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Neonatology, Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar, from 1st Nov 2024 till 30th April 2025 following approval from the institutional ethical review board [IRB# 2186] and Research and Evaluation Unit CPSP [Ref No. CPSP/REU/PED-2023-021-7593]. The sample size was calculated using the World Health Organization's sample size estimation formula for a single proportion, with a 95% confidence level ($Z = 1.96$), an expected prevalence of 15% for indirect hyperbilirubinemia in preterm infants from a local study⁶ and an absolute precision of 5% resulting in a minimal sample size of 196 individuals. Non-probability consecutive sampling was used to enroll 196 preterm neonates in total. Regardless of gender, neonates with a gestational age at delivery between 28 and 36 weeks and ages ranging from 1 to 28 days met the inclusion criteria. Indirect hyperbilirubinemia was defined as a serum total bilirubin level greater than 1.5 mg/dL with an indirect bilirubin fraction exceeding 1.2 mg/dL, as determined by a venous blood sample examined in a hospital laboratory. Premature neonates were defined as those born before 37 full weeks of gestation.

To minimize confounding, neonates with syndromic characteristics, Rh incompatibility, macrosomia, maternal diabetes mellitus, or moms with hemoglobinopathies were excluded from the study. Parents or legal guardians provided written informed consent following eligibility screening. Age in days, gestational age at birth, gender, delivery method, birth weight, domicile, maternal education, father occupation, and socioeconomic status were among the demographic and baseline clinical data that were documented. Each newborn had a 5 mL venous blood sample taken aseptically, which was then sent to the hospital lab to assess the levels of total and indirect serum bilirubin. A skilled pathologist who was blind to the patients' clinical information examined every sample. In accordance with the operational definitions, the existence or lack of indirect hyperbilirubinemia was recorded on a standardized proforma.

Results:

Our study enrolled total of 196 patients fulfilling inclusion criteria. The average gestational age (\pm SD) at delivery was 33.26 ± 2.34 weeks, with a mean age at time of assessment was 5.45 ± 3.59 days and a mean birth weight of 1.88 ± 0.43 kg. Males made up 58.2% of the sample, 53.1% were delivered via cesarean section, and 56.1% were from rural areas. 41.8% of mothers had secondary education, 36.2% had none or primary education, and 22.0% had college or higher education. Nearly half (48.5%) of the newborns belonged to the lowest socioeconomic status. Table 1 shows a thorough demographic and baseline clinical profile. Total, indirect, and direct serum bilirubin levels averaged 2.07 ± 1.07 mg/dL, 1.55 ± 0.83 mg/dL,

Data was analyzed using SPSS Version 25. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to determine if the quantitative variables such as age, gestational age, birth weight, and serum bilirubin levels were normal. The results were reported as mean \pm standard deviation or median with interquartile range, as applicable. Frequencies and percentages were used to represent categorical factors, including indirect hyperbilirubinemia, gender, mode of delivery, and socioeconomic level. To account for effect modifiers, indirect hyperbilirubinemia was stratified by gender, birth weight, gestational age, age in days, and delivery method. When necessary, Fisher's exact test or the chi-square test was used for post-stratification comparisons. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value of less than 0.05.

and 0.52 ± 0.28 mg/dL. Overall, 51 of 196 newborns (26.0%) met the operational criteria for indirect hyperbilirubinemia (IHB). 68.6% of individuals affected had mild illness, 27.5% moderate, and 3.9% severe hyperbilirubinemia. The results are summarized in Table 2.

On stratification (Table 3), gestational age had a statistically significant correlation with IHB ($p = 0.012$). The prevalence of IHB was highest among neonates born at 28-31 weeks (42.5%), followed by 20.1% at 32-33 weeks and 21.3% at 34-36 weeks. There was no significant connection found for gender ($p = 1.000$), mode of delivery ($p = 0.691$), birth weight category ($p = 0.334$), location of residence ($p = 0.889$), or socioeconomic status ($p = 0.517$). Figure 1 depicts the gradient in IHB frequency by gestational age category.

Result

Table 1. Descriptive analysis of baseline characteristics of Premature Neonates (n = 196)

Variable	Value
Age at assessment (days), Mean \pm SD	5.45 ± 3.59

Gestational age (weeks), Mean ± SD		33.26 ± 2.34
Birth weight (kg), Mean ± SD		1.88 ± 0.43
Gestational age category:	28-31 weeks	40 (20.4%)
	32-33 weeks	65 (33.2%)
	34-36 weeks	91 (46.4%)
Gender:	Male	114 (58.2%)
	Female	82 (41.8%)
Mode of delivery:	Normal vaginal delivery	92 (46.9%)
	Cesarean section	104 (53.1%)
Place of residence:	Rural	110 (56.1%)
	Urban	86 (43.9%)
Maternal education:	None/Primary	71 (36.2%)
	Secondary	82 (41.8%)
	College	43 (22.0%)
Father profession:	Laborer	75 (38.3%)
	Skilled/Clerical	82 (41.8%)
	Professional/Business	39 (19.9%)
Socioeconomic status:	Low	95 (48.5%)
	Middle	81 (41.3%)
	High	20 (10.2%)

Table 2A: Descriptive analysis of Serum Bilirubin Levels (n = 196)

Variable	Minimum	Maximum	Mean ± SD
Total serum bilirubin (mg/dL)	0.60	6.90	2.07 ± 1.07
Indirect serum bilirubin (mg/dL)	0.50	6.20	1.55 ± 0.83
Direct serum bilirubin (mg/dL)	0.10	1.20	0.52 ± 0.28

Table 2B: Frequency Distribution Analysis of Indirect Hyperbilirubinemia (n = 196)

Variables		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Indirect hyperbilirubinemia status	Absent	145	74.0
	Present	51	26.0
Severity of IHB	Mild (1.2 - 3.0 mg/dL)	35	68.6
	Moderate (3.1 - 6.0 mg/dL)	14	27.5

Severe (> 6.0 mg/dL)	2	3.9
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Table 3: Stratified Analysis of Indirect Hyperbilirubinemia by Demographic and Clinical Variables (Chi-square / Fisher's Exact Test)

Variables	Categories	n	IHB Yes	IHB No	IHB %	p-value
Gestational age (weeks)	28-31	40	17	23	42.5	
	32-33	65	13	52	20.1	
	34-36	91	21	70	21.3	0.012
Gender	Male	114	30	84	26.3	
	Female	82	21	61	25.6	1.000
Mode of delivery	NVD	92	22	70	23.9	
	Cesarean	104	29	75	27.9	0.691
Birth weight (kg)	< 1.5	54	16	38	29.6	
	1.5 - < 2.0	61	15	46	24.6	
	2.0 - < 2.5	57	13	44	22.8	
	≥ 2.5	24	7	17	29.2	0.334
Residence	Rural	110	29	81	26.4	
	Urban	86	22	64	25.6	0.889
Socioeconomic status	Low	95	28	67	29.5	
	Middle	81	18	63	22.2	
	High	20	5	15	25.0	0.517

Figure 1: Indirect Hyperbilirubinemia by GA category (n=196)

Discussion:

The prevalence of indirect hyperbilirubinemia in this study was 26%, with the majority of cases being mild and the maximum prevalence reported in neonates born at 28-31 weeks gestation. This is consistent with recent global data, which show that preterm children are still at the highest risk of neonatal jaundice, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where system limitations and early gestational deliveries coexist^{7,8}. The low incidence of severe cases is a result of early bilirubin detection, systematic monitoring, and timely phototherapy in the NICU. This pattern is consistent with international experience since the implementation of the 2022 AAP guideline, which includes systematic bilirubin monitoring, escalation triggers, and structured follow-up, indirectly benefiting even preterm children^{9,10}. Similar benefits have been observed following institutional adoption of evidence-based policies that are consistent with NICE recommendations^{11,12}.

Gestational age was the only variable that was substantially linked with indirect hyperbilirubinemia, with the risk being higher during earlier gestations. This conclusion is compatible with the molecular mechanisms of immature bilirubin conjugation and higher bilirubin load in preterms, as revealed in LMIC NICU cohorts^{14,15}. In contrast, no correlation was detected with gender, corroborating meta-analytic findings that male sex is not an independent predictor when maturity is taken into account⁸. Similar null results have been reported in Ethiopian NICU investigations^{14,15}. The risk of hyperbilirubinemia was unaffected by the mode of delivery. Although previous research connected instrumental delivery to elevated bilirubin levels via cephalohematoma, more recent hospital-based investigations found no such effect in units with universal bilirubin screening and early intervention¹⁴.

In our population, there was no significant connection between birth weight and indirect

hyperbilirubinemia. This is presumably due to the small weight range in a preterm-only group. Regional NICU studies with similar approaches have produced consistent findings¹⁷. Sociodemographic characteristics such as domicile, maternal education, and socioeconomic position also showed no connection, as is typical of hospital-based research with standardized methods to reduce demographic differences. However, lack of community knowledge, presentation delays, and inadequate follow-up procedures are well-documented issues in Pakistan and other LMIC settings^{13,18,19}. These variables may not affect disease occurrence in hospitalized neonates, but they do have an impact on severity and outcomes at the community level.

These findings highlight the need for established newborn jaundice therapy routes. Early bilirubin measurement, adherence to defined phototherapy thresholds, and rigorous follow-up protocols have all reduced the prevalence of severe illness in several tertiary NICUs^{9-12,16}. Additional initiatives, such as improving parental education and community referral systems, are needed to address the delays and gaps observed outside of hospital settings^{18,19}. Predictive methods like gestation-based nomograms and multivariable risk models have helped to improve risk categorization and personalized care planning^{20,21}.

The study has significant drawbacks. The study's generalizability is limited because it was conducted at a single site. The cross-sectional design prevents causal inference, and the restricted variation of gestational age and birth weight may limit statistical power to find secondary relationships. The exclusion of hemolytic illness allowed for a more concentrated estimation of IHB, but it limited comparability with all-cause jaundice populations. Finally, fixed laboratory cut-offs were employed instead of gestation-specific thresholds, which may result in modest classification discrepancies when compared to guideline-based categorization^{9-11,16}.

In conclusion, roughly one in every four preterm newborns admitted to our NICU had indirect

hyperbilirubinemia, with the risk concentrated in early gestational age groups and the disease severity being largely moderate. Gestational age was found to be the most important driver, with no significant associations with gender, delivery style, birth weight, or sociodemographic characteristics. These findings are consistent with previous national and international research, emphasizing the need of early screening, structured phototherapy regimens, and community awareness strategies for reducing severe hyperbilirubinemia in low- and middle-income countries⁷⁻²¹.

References:

- Kong X, Xu F, Wu R, Wu H, Ju R, Zhao X, et al. Neonatal mortality and morbidity among infants between 24 to 31 complete weeks: A multicenter survey in China from 2013 to 2014. *BMC Pediatr.* 2016; 16:174-7.
- Tsai M, Lien R, Chiang M, Hsu J, Fu R, Chu S, et al. Prevalence and morbidity of late preterm infants: Current status in a medical center of Northern Taiwan. *Pediatrics & Neonatology.* 2012; 53: 171-7.
- Shaprio-Mendoza CK, Lackritz EM. Epidemiology of late and moderate preterm birth. *Semin Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2012; 17(3):120-5.
- van der Schoor LW, Dijk PH, Verkade HJ, Kamsma AC, Schreuder AB, Groen H, et al. Unconjugated free bilirubin in preterm infants. *Early Hum Dev.* 2017; 106- 7:25-32.
- Schonhaut L, Pérez M, Muñoz S. Association between neonatal morbidity, gestational age and developmental delays in moderate to late preterm children. *Rev Child Pediatr.* 2015; 86:415-25.
- Bajwa FE, Sarwar I, Alam Mahboob, Nawaz MR, Bahawal S. Frequency of hypocalcemia and indirect hyperbilirubinemia in preterm babies remain admitted in Independent University Hospital. *Professional Med J* 2019; 26(9):1557-61.
- Diala UM, Usman F, Appiah D, Hassan L, Ogundele T, Abdullahi F, et al. Global prevalence of severe neonatal jaundice among hospital admissions: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Clin Med.* 2023;12(11):3738. doi:10.3390/jcm12113738.

- Lin Q, Zhu D, Chen C, Feng Y, Shen F, Wu Z. Risk factors for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Transl Pediatr.* 2022;11(6):1001-9. doi:10.21037/tp-22-229.
- Kemper AR, Newman TB, Slaughter JL, Maisels MJ, Watchko JF, Downs SM, et al. Clinical Practice Guideline Revision: Management of Hyperbilirubinemia in the Newborn Infant 35 or More Weeks of Gestation. *Pediatrics.* 2022;150(3):e2022058859. doi:10.1542/peds.2022-058859.
- Okulu E, Ergenekon E, Erdevi O. Bilirubin measurement and phototherapy use after the 2022 AAP guideline: what changed? *Pediatrics.* 2024;153(5):e2023065999.
- Ansong-Assoku B, Kandamany N, Osei-Akoto A. Neonatal jaundice. In: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024.
- National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE). Jaundice in newborn babies under 28 days (CG98 update). London: NICE; 2023.
- Usha Rani Kandula, Dwivedi M, Singh S, Verma S, Gupta S. Knowledge regarding neonatal jaundice and its management among staff nurses. *Int J Res Paediatr Nurs.* 2024;6(1):52-61. doi:10.33545/26641291.2024.v6.i1a.155.
- Tessema M, Aweke Z, Abate A, Asmare M. Magnitude and associated factors of neonatal jaundice among NICU admissions in Dessie Town public hospitals, Ethiopia: a multicenter cross-sectional study. *Front Pediatr.* 2024;12:1288604. doi:10.3389/fped.2024.1288604.
- Ayalew T, Molla A, Kefale B, Alene TD, Abebe GK, Ngusie HS, et al. Factors associated with neonatal jaundice among neonates admitted at referral hospitals in northeast Ethiopia: a facility-based unmatched case-control study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2024;24(1):150. doi:10.1186/s12884-024-06352-y.
- Johns Hopkins All Children's Hospital. Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia clinical pathway. St. Petersburg (FL): JHACH; 2023.
- Ashraf MW, Munir I, Munir N, Waheed K, Mubarak B, Kausar S, Mehmood S, et al. Incidence and patterns of neonatal jaundice in tertiary medical facility. *J Popul Ther Clin Pharmacol.* 2024;31(1):1825-31. doi:10.53555/jptcp.v31i1.3908.
- Naeem H, Ullah K, Ochani S, Naeem K, Ahmad HB, Hasibuzzaman MA. The need for neonatal jaundice screening awareness in the Pakistani population: short communication. *Ann Med Surg (Lond).* 2023;85:4187-9. doi:10.1097/MS9.0000000000000960.
- Donkor DR, Asare A, Tetteh J, Obeng B, Osei A. Neonatal jaundice management: knowledge, attitude, and practices among nurses and midwives. *Nurs Rep.* 2023;13(3):1204-17. doi:10.3390/nursrep13030103.
- Wang S, Wang C, Zheng S, Dou H, Qu D, Wang Y, et al. Easy-to-use nomogram to predict neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. *PeerJ.* 2025;13:e20017. doi:10.7717/peerj.20017.
- Al-Rabeeh D, Al-Majmaie Z, Saleem I, et al. Association between birth weight and severity of neonatal jaundice: a case-control study. *Cureus.* 2025;17(10):e93966. doi:10.7759/cureus.93966